

FEMALE CONSUMER PREFERENCE AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS SELECTED MASALA PRODUCTS

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Cite This Article: Dr. R. Manikandan & S. Senthil Priya, "Female Consumer Preference and Satisfaction Towards Selected Masala Products", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 211-215, 2018.

Abstract:

There are many companies involved in manufacturing Masala Products all over the country. As of now, many varieties of Masala Products are available in the market which we use for preparing Vegetarian as well as Non-Vegetarian items. The Masala food items usually give the same taste as like Traditional Cooking. As it is always available in the nearby shop, people can get the Masala Products at their door steps too. Hence, the Masala Products becomes an essential in everybody's life in fast running world. The main objectives of the study is to identify the preference to purchase of Masala powders among women consumers and to know the consumers level of preference towards masala powders. The data for the study has been collected in primary through issue of structured questionnaire. A sample of 221 customers who are living in Pollachi Taluk have been selected by adopting convenience sampling method. Simple percentage, Weighted average ranking, Friedman Rank Analysis, chi-square test and ANOVA test are applied to process the data and draw inferences.

Introduction:

India has traditionally been known for its spice and culinary herb production and it is one of the largest spice producing and consuming countries. Spices are essential ingredients adding taste and flavouring in food preparations. India is the largest producer and consumer of spices with a production of around 36.68 lakh tones. Indian spices are of the finest quality and its excellent cuisine, it's unique regions of cooking, and a pleasant dining experience. The use of Ready Mix Masala plays an important role in the modern day-to-day life. Most of the people prefer using Masala Products in order to save their time and energy to cook a variety of food easily. There are many companies involved in manufacturing Masala Products all over the country. As of now, many varieties of Masala Products are available in the market which we use for preparing Vegetarian as well as Non-Vegetarian items. The Masala food items usually give the same taste as like Traditional Cooking. As it is always available in the nearby shop, people can get the Masala Products at their door steps too. Hence, the Masala Products becomes an essential in everybody's life in fast running world.

Review of Literature:

Buveneswari et al (2013) in their study entitled "Fast moving consumer goods marketing with special reference to sakthi masala products", to know the opinion about the attributes of sakthi masala. They find that, the majority of the respondents identify the product through the brand name and quality of the product. Ramesh et al (2013) in their study on "Brand preference and factors influencing the purchasing of masala products in Tirupur", to find the brand preference, and factors that influence the purchasing of masala product. They find that, the consumers prefer sakthi masala products Convenience, savings time are the influencing factors while purchase of masala products. Poonam Begal (2015) carried out her study on "Consumer buying behaviour towards spices with special reference to everest masala in bengaluru city", the aim of the study is to identify the consumer buying behaviour and the level of satisfaction towards spices. She finds that, the satisfaction level is very high among people with regard to everest masala and quality followed by size, availability, brand name, packaging, promotion, price and reference group are influencing factors for buying behaviour towards spices.

Statement of the Problem:

Now-a-days peoples are readying to buy the masala products from the neighbouring shop. Three decades ago, womens' are cooking masala food in their home itself. But now in their busy schedule they also buy and using the masala powders. Most of the women's are also ready to but masala powder and using it for their food preparation. Women consumers are need to know the variety of masala powders, and its various brands of masala powders to consuming their family. In this statement induced to rise the questions like a) What is the consumer behavior of masala powders b) Women's satisfaction of masala products

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the socio economic profile of the female consumers
- ✓ To know the female consumers level of preference towards masala powders.
- ✓ To find out the female consumers level of satisfaction on masala powders.

Methodology:

The present study is mainly based on primary data which is collected from 221 consumers in Pollachi Taluk through issue of structured questionnaire which contains questions relating to the Socio-economic profile

of sample respondents, Details of using masala products, Preference and opinion on masala products and level of satisfaction of using masala powders. Necessary guidance was given to the respondents for filling up the questionnaire. Convenience sampling method is adopted to select the female consumers in Pollachi taluk. Statistical tools like Simple percentage test and Chi-square test are used to analyse the data.

Findings:

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile of Sample Consumers

Particulars	No. of Consumers	Percentage
Area of Residence		
Rural	148	67.00
Semi- Urban	73	33.00
Age Group		
Up to 30 Years	101	45.70
31-40 Years	57	25.80
41-60 Years	59	26.70
Above 60 Years	4	1.80
Marital Status		
Married	160	72.40
Unmarried	61	27.60
Educational Qualification		
Up to HSC	87	39.37
Diploma	22	9.95
Under-Graduation level	56	25.34
Post-Graduation level	32	14.48
Professional	24	10.86
Occupation		
Home Maker	73	33.03
Private Sector Employee	62	28.05
Government Sector Employee	6	2.71
Business	20	9.04
Agriculturist	16	7.23
Professional	20	9.04
Students	24	10.90
Type of Family		
Joint	51	23.08
Nuclear	170	76.92
Earning Members in the Family		
One	72	32.58
Two	112	50.68
Three & above	37	16.74
Non-Earning Members in the Family		
One	79	35.75
Two	95	42.99
Above two	47	21.26
Number of Members in the Family		
Up to three	85	38.46
Four	96	43.44
Above four	40	18.10
Family Monthly Income Per month		
Up to ₹.20000	146	66.06
₹.20,001 to ₹.40,000	45	20.37
₹.40,001 to ₹.60,000	25	11.31
Above ₹.60,000	5	2.26
Preferred Mode		
Wholesale Stores	45	20.40
Retail Stores	51	23.10
Convenience Shop	38	17.20
Departmental Stores	87	39.40
Period of using Masala Powders		

Particulars	No. of Consumers	Percentage
Less than a year	43	19.50
One to two years	46	20.80
Above three years	132	59.70
Purchase Frequency of Masala Powders		
Once –in –a week	61	27.60
Fortnightly	8	3.60
Monthly	125	56.60
Quarterly	13	5.90
Occasionally	14	6.30
Usage of Masala Powders		
Always	56	25.30
Occasionally	44	19.90
Sometimes	90	40.70
Often	16	7.20
Never	15	6.80
Amount Spend on Masala Powders		
Up to ₹.100	79	35.70
₹.101 to ₹.200	89	40.30
₹.201 to ₹.300	33	14.90
Above ₹.300	20	9.00
Purchasing Quantity		
50gm	50	22.60
100gm	106	48.00
200gm	32	14.50
250gm	24	10.90
500gm	9	4.10
Purpose of Using		
Vegetarian	24	10.90
Non-Vegetarian	48	21.70
Both	149	67.40

From the table 1 reveals that:

- ✓ Majority of 148(67.00%) consumers are residing in rural area.
- ✓ Most of 101(45.70%) consumers age is up to 30 years.
- ✓ Majority of 160(72.40%) consumers are married.
- ✓ Most of 87(38.90%) consumers having Educational qualification is up to HSC.
- ✓ Most of the consumers, 73(33.03%) are home makers.
- ✓ Majority of 170(76.92%) consumers belong to nuclear family.
- ✓ Majority of 112(50.68%) consumers have two earning members in the family
- ✓ Most of the 95(42.99%) consumers have two non-earning members in their family.
- ✓ Most of 96(43.44%) consumers have four members in their family.
- ✓ Majority of the 146(66.06%) consumers family income per month is up to Rs.20, 000.

Details of using Masala Powders:

- ✓ Majority of the consumers, 204(92.31%) are using sakthi followed by Aachi, Annapoorna, MTR, JP, Kannan, Everest, ITC, Krishna and Nirapara.
- ✓ Most of 87(39.40%) consumers preferred to purchase masala powders in departmental stores.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers, 132(59.70%) are using the masala powders for above three years.
- ✓ Majority of 125(56.60%) consumers purchase the masala powders on monthly basis.
- ✓ Most of the consumers, 90(40.70%) are using the masala powders for sometimes.
- ✓ Most of 89(40.30%) consumers spend Rs.101 to Rs.200 per month for purchasing the masala powders.
- ✓ Most of the consumers, 106(48.00%) are buying 100gm packets.
- ✓ Most of 149(67.40%) consumers are using the masala powders for vegetarian as well as the non-vegetarian.

Variables Influencing Level of Satisfaction:

Eleven variables namely Area, Age, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Occupation, Type of family, Earning members in the family, Non-earning members in the family, Total number of members in the family, Family income per month, Period of using masala powders have been selected in order to test if there really exists any association between each of the variables and level of satisfaction. Chi-square test has been

made use to study association between the variables and the level of satisfaction. Level of significance chosen five percentage.

Table 2: Selected variables and level of satisfaction on masala products

Variables	χ^2 Value	D.F	Table value
			5% level
Area	1.576	2	5.991
Age	7.565	6	12.592
Marital status	6.209	2	5.991
Educational Qualification	5.673	8	15.507
Occupation	17.474*	12	21.026
Type of family	1.229	2	5.991
Number of earning members in the family	0.602	4	9.488
Number of non-earning members in the family	0.879	4	9.488
Total number of members in the family	1.451	4	9.488
Family income per month	2.556	6	12.592
Period of using instant food products	9.813*	4	9.488

*Significant at five per cent level

The table above discloses that out of the total eleven variables selected, four variables are found to be significant with the consumers level of satisfaction on masala products. Of them two variables namely occupation, period of using masala products are significantly associated with the consumers' level of satisfaction at five percent level.

Suggestions:

Based on the findings of the study and the opinion given by the consumers at the time of data collection, the following suggestions are put forth.

- ✓ To increase the quality of masala powders and reduce the harmful contents mixing in the masala powders.
- ✓ To increase the taste and freshness by adding the healthy ingredients.
- ✓ The producers should avoid using too many Preservatives, Artificial colours and Harmful elements in to the masala powders.
- ✓ The producers should not use any chemical for maintaining the freshness and smell of the masala powders.

Conclusion:

The study found that, the variables namely, Area of Residence, Age, Educational Qualification, Occupation, Type of Family, Number of Earning members in the Family, Number of Non-Earning members in the Family, Total Number of members in the Family and Family Income are found to be not associated with the level of satisfaction. Marital Status and Period of using masala products are associated with the level of satisfaction.

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